

Versatility of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene implants in orthopaedic treatments: principles and applications

Philippe Buttin¹, François Fauqueux², Fabrice Bernard³, Bastien Goin^{4,5,6}, Helene Le Pommelet⁷, Antonin Crumiere⁶, Herve Brissot⁸, Pablo Rivier⁹, Jonathan Pink¹⁰, Benito de la Puerta¹¹, Elvin Kulendra¹¹, Eric Vigier⁴, Thibaut Cachon⁴

¹Itinerant surgeon, VETECHOCHIR CRMB, Annecy-Villaz, France

²Animed Veterinary Clinic, Gap, France

³Saint Martin The Alps Veterinary Hospital, Allonzier la Caille, France

⁴University of Lyon, VetAgro Sup, Interactions Cellules Environnement (ICE), Marcy l'Etoile, France

⁵Univ Lyon, University Gustave Eiffel, Univ Claude Bernard Lyon 1, LBMC UMR_T9406, Lyon, France

⁶Novetech Surgery, Monaco

⁷Ottawa Animal Emergency and Specialty Hospital, Ottawa, Ontario, Canada

⁸AzurVet Referral Veterinary Center, Saint-Laurent-du-Var, France

⁹OnlyVet Veterinary Hospital Center, Saint-Priest, France

¹⁰Willows Veterinary Centre & Referral Service, West Midlands, United Kingdom

¹¹North Downs Specialist Referrals, Bletchingley, United Kingdom

Abstract: Ligament and tendon injuries are diverse and can be complex to treat according to their gravity and chronicity (time from injury to diagnostics and then to surgical treatment). Treatments might involve temporary to permanent joint immobilization that can result in total, partial, or limited recovery of the physiological range of motion of an articulation. Moreover, the prosthetic material used for the treatment can be suited for a given pathology but limited for another due to its design, its fixation system, or its biomechanical resistance; making a necessity to get experienced with diverse surgical procedures and equipment. For instance, for hip stabilisation, treatments include capsulorrhaphy, prosthetic capsule repair, rectus femoris suture, deep gluteal muscle fixation, the De Vita technique, trochanteric transposition, extra-articular iliofemoral suture secured with anchors, intra-articular replacement of the femoral head ligament with a synthetic ligament secured by toggles, or transarticular pinning. For Achilles tendon repair, this includes different types of sutures with fixation of the pathological limb in hyperextension by external fixator, but also other techniques like calcaneo-tibial screw, autologous graft, metallic tendon plating, polyurethan or polypropylene mesh graft, or polyethylene terephthalate braided implant among others. In this aspect, braided synthetic implant made of ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) and secured by cortical button and/or interference screws through bone tunnels represents a concrete versatile solution that respect the physiological insertions of the ligaments and tendons since it replaces disrupted ligaments and provides support for the healing or augmentation of damaged tendons from various articulations. The ultimate goal is to stabilize the disrupted articulations while preserving their anatomical physiology by eliminating the use of external fixators replaced by a less rigid external coaptation system such as bi-valve resins. The UHMWPE implant and its fixations have shown a high biomechanical resistance *ex-vivo* for diverse pathologies such as the reconstruction of canine cranial cruciate ligament (1, 2) and feline hip luxation (3). Here, we present how the implant features have been applied clinically for the reconstruction of the round ligament and Achilles tendon in dogs.

Keywords: Achilles tendon, Dog, Hip luxation, Orthopaedic surgery, UHMWPE implant.

1. CANINE COXOFEMORAL LUXATION MANAGEMENT

Coxofemoral luxation (CFL) accounts for 90% of cases of joint luxation in dogs, mainly caused by trauma. Current treatments include extra- or intra-articular stabilization of the hip joint by iliofemoral suture or various synthetic implants, generally using toggle pins for acetabular fixation.

An eight-year-old male bearded collie was referred for left traumatic CFL subsequent to a dog fight. The orthopaedic examination of the CF joint revealed pain and cracking, and a dorsal displacement of the greater trochanter (Figure 1A, B). X-rays confirmed the diagnosis and discreet osteoarthritis was observed. Surgical treatment was performed by primary ligament repair, followed by the insertion of an UHMWPE implant (Novalig platine, Novetech Surgery, Monaco) which was pre-assembled with a cortical button. The cortical button was implanted on the acetabulum through a drilled tunnel. The implant was then passed through a tunnel drilled from the distal base of the trochanter to the femoral head allowing an intra-articular

reconstruction of the round ligament. The implant was then secured with an interference screw in a second femoral tunnel, perpendicular to the first tunnel, allowing an appropriate tensioning of the implant. Immediate postoperative X-rays showed that the implantation of the interference screw followed the drilling axis (Figure 1C, D). The dog started using the operated hindlimb one day postoperatively. At four weeks postoperatively, orthopaedic examination showed no lameness nor pain during mobilization, nor loss of joint mobility in the contralateral hindlimb. Four-week postoperative X-rays showed perfect coaptation of the operated coxofemoral joint.

Reconstruction of the round ligament using an UHMWPE implant fixed by an acetabular cortical button and a femoral interference screw was an early success in this case report, as shown by postoperative X-rays and orthopaedic control. However, owing to the short postoperative follow-up period, this result needs to be confirmed.

Figure 1. Pre- (A, B) and immediate post-operative (C, D) radiographs of round ligament reconstruction with an UHMWPE implant secured by cortical button and an interference screw.

2. 37 CASES OF CANINE ACHILLES TENDON REPAIR

Immobilization after Achilles tendon repair remains challenging and associated with a high rate of complications. The aim of this study is to report clinical outcome and complications in the use of an ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) implant with minimal post-operative immobilization.

Thirty-five dogs from nine referral centres were included. Data from November 2018 to December 2022 were collected. All repairs were performed using a UHMWPE implant (Novaten, Novetech Surgery, Monaco) secured to the proximal native tendon with a modified overlock suture technique and to the calcaneus using a two tunnels technique and an interference screw (4). Post operative immobilization consisted of four to six weeks of lateral splint. Clinical outcome was subjective evaluation from the surgeons based on orthopaedic examination. Thirty-seven repairs were included in this study. Mean duration of follow up was 8,6 months (1-34 m, \pm 8,6). Eleven major complications (29,7%) were reported, including 8 post-operative infections (21,6%), 3 repair failures (8,1%) and 1 calcaneal fracture (2,7%). Four patients required an arthrodesis (10,8%). All patients requiring implants removal had a normal stance afterward. Outcome was good to excellent in 35/37 cases (96.5%). No catastrophic failure was reported.

The use of a synthetic tendon as an internal bracing in Achilles tendon repair is a procedure that should be considered among other traditional techniques, according to those preliminary results. This study showed that if the tendon healed properly over the implant, it was feasible and safe to remove the implants.

3. CONCLUSIONS

UHMWPE implants offer a high versatility of utilization allowing to treat a large range of ligament and tendon pathologies such as hip luxation and Achilles tendon rupture. This is due to both the implant design and its fixation system that adapt to various type of morphology and articulations, making it a promising and valuable alternative to current treatments. Further clinical results must be collected to confirm these encouraging results.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We thank the service of surgery of the veterinary school VetAgro Sup, University of Lyon, for the test and development of several surgical procedures that involved the use of UHMWPE implants.

5. REFERENCES

1. Blanc, Q. et al., "Effect of the number of interference screws for the fixation of an intra-articular cranial cruciate ligament prosthesis in dogs: Biomechanical study," *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 22, no. sup1, pp. S102–S104, 2019, doi: 10.1080/10255842.2020.1713496.
2. Goin, B. et al., "Biomechanical analysis of a ligament fixation system for CCL reconstruction in a canine cadaver model," *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 22, no. sup1, pp. S109–S111, 2019, doi: 10.1080/10255842.2020.1713499.
3. Letesson, J. et al., "Validation of a biomechanical testing protocol of craniodorsal hip luxation in feline cadavers and comparison of two ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene materials used for extra-articular hip stabilisation," *Journal of Feline Medicine and Surgery*, vol. 24, no. 10, pp. e360–e369, 2022, doi: 10.1177/1098612X221114851.
4. Buttin, P. et al., "Repair of Tendon Disruption Using a Novel Synthetic Fiber Implant in Dogs and Cats: The Surgical Procedure and Three Case Reports," *Veterinary Medicine International*, vol. 2020, pp. 1–9, 2020, doi: 10.1155/2020/4146790.